

See discussions, stats, and author profiles for this publication at: <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/379819686>

WOMEN IN THE DIGITAL STREAMS OF HISTORY. WOMEN'S THEMES ON POLISH YOUTUBE HISTORY CHANNELS

Article in *Historyka Studia Metodologiczne* · December 2023

CITATIONS

0

READS

54

8 authors, including:

Wiktor Werner

Adam Mickiewicz University in Poznań

54 PUBLICATIONS 67 CITATIONS

SEE PROFILE

Zuzanna Szymczak

Adam Mickiewicz University in Poznań

2 PUBLICATIONS 0 CITATIONS

SEE PROFILE

Nell Sypniewska

Adam Mickiewicz University in Poznań

4 PUBLICATIONS 0 CITATIONS

SEE PROFILE

Borys Staszak

Adam Mickiewicz University in Poznań

1 PUBLICATION 0 CITATIONS

SEE PROFILE

Wiktor Werner (UAM), Nell Sypniewska (UAM), Zuzanna Szymczak (UAM), Maciej Stachura (UAM), Adam Strykowski (UAM), Borys Staszak (UAM), Adrian Trzoss (UAM), Cyprian Kleist

Women in the digital streams of history. Women's themes on Polish YouTube history channels, *Historyka Studia Metodologiczne* (2023): 409-435.

Research funded by the NCN grant № 2020/39/B/HS3/01237

Keywords: YouTube, Web 2.0, herstory, historical narrative, correspondence analysis

Abstract:

In this article, the authors confront the thesis found in historical discourse about the dominance of male figures in historical narratives. In order to do so, they analyse the new research field that is the social networking site YouTube and the most popular channels on historical topics contained therein. The main research question is whether women are marginalised in the narratives contained in the sources discussed, in which contexts they appear and what is the reception of the films in which they appear. In addition, the authors look at the question of the form of historical narratives. The study combines quantitative methods (descriptive statistics, correspondence analysis) as well as qualitative methods (Northrop Frye's typology of story motifs). For this purpose, 551 films were analysed and then annotated using seven groups of tags corresponding to the content of the sources - concerning the functioning of female characters and the subject matter of the films. As a result of the analyses carried out, it was observed that the thesis of the absolute dominance of male characters in historical narratives does not fully hold true under the conditions of Web 2.0 sources in terms of quantity, while in terms of content it cannot be accepted unreservedly in the context of the very diverse use of female themes in social media resources.

1. Research problem:

The article is dedicated to the question of the presence of women as protagonists of the multimedia productions presented on the Polish-speaking YouTube. The research problem of the text refers to the thesis found in the literature of the subject that historical narrative is an area dominated by men both as the authors of this narrative and the protagonists of historical events.¹ It can be inferred from the above thesis that, in historical descriptions of the world, women appear to a lesser extent than they are actually present in historical events because either the authors of such descriptions are not inclined to show the actual role of women in history or the recipients of various narrative forms are not interested in women as subjects of history.

Our research interest focuses on the peculiar form of historical narrative (story) which is the multimedia production presented on YouTube. A special feature of these productions, found in private channels, is that they depend on the financing and other activities of recipients which determine the reach of films (due to recommendation algorithms). Due to monetisation (the ability to gain advertising remuneration dependent, among other things, on the number of views), as well as partnerships (marketing campaigns, product placement) and the direct financial support from viewers (e.g., via the Patronite service), channel owners are keenly interested in maintaining contact with their viewers and in satisfying their needs by providing appropriate knowledge and entertainment. We assume then, that the specificity of films created so is linked to the expectations of the channel's viewers. The presence or absence of female figures in the productions of historical YouTube channels (regarding the

¹ Iwona Chmura-Rutkowska, Edyta Głowacka-Sobiech, Izabela Skórzyńska, “«Niegodne historii». O nieobecności kobiet w dziejach w kontekście analiz wybranych podręczników do nauki historii w Polsce”, *Sensus Historiae* 13, 4 (2013): [no pagination]; Izabela Skórzyńska, “Historia. Raport przedmiotowy”, in *Gender w podręcznikach Projekt badawczy. Raport*, t. III, red. Iwona Chmura-Rutkowska, Maciej Duda, Marta Mazurek, Aleksandra Sołtysiak-Łuczak (Warszawa: Fundacja Feminoteka, 2016), 7–38; Billie Melman, “History and Memory: the Invention of Women's Past in the Nineteenth and Early Twentieth Centuries”, *History and Memory* 5, 1 (1993): 5–41; Sabrina Ebbersmeyer, “From a «Memorable Place» to «Drops in the Ocean»: On the Marginalization of Women Philosophers in German Historiography of Philosophy”, *British Journal for the History of Philosophy*, 28, 3 (2020): 442–462; Brahim El Guabli, “Gender-Unaware History: Ordinary Women as the Forgotten of Moroccan Historiography of the Present”, *Journal of Applied Language and Culture Studies* 2 (2019), 57–78; Charl Bignaut, “Untold History with a Historiography: A Review of Scholarship on Afrikaner Women in South African History”, *South African Historical Journal* 65, 4 (2013), 596–617; Daria Hejwosz-Gromkowska, Dobrochna Hildebrandt-Wypych, “Solidarity Movement in the School History Textbooks in Poland-Selected Contexts of Gender, Religion and Politics”, *Pedagogy, Culture & Society* (2022): 1–18.

most popular ones and those of clearly commercial nature) is not just a private initiative of the makers of such films: it also follows the particular expectations of viewers, since (content) creators and their recipients exist in a mutual positive interaction (feedback) system. It is the fundamental feature driving the Web 2.0 phenomenon, that is, such a reorientation of communication between senders and recipients in social media that both exist in a continuous and constantly changing relationship. Such interactivity takes not only the form of the already mentioned financing but also “thumbs up” and “thumbs down” reactions and discussions in comments², which constitutes clear feedback for the authors of the production on how their materials were received.

Our research covers not only the subject matter and content of films but their reception (number of views) as well. Therefore, we are considering both the creation of the narrative and its social reception, concerning which the strong position of YouTube as the medium to gain historical knowledge is an important fact.³

The next research problem in our article is the context in which women are presented in historical productions on the YouTube platform. Both qualitative research methods (based on the analysis of film content) and quantitative (using film metadata) were employed in that part. Films were annotated (using categorised tags⁴) with regard to the extent to which women’s themes were present and to the nature of those themes: geolocation, chronological period, and how the film’s main figure was framed. The purpose of the tagging was to study the quantitative relationships between the specificity of framing women in films and the other thematic properties of films.

2. Methodological remarks

2.1

The empirical basis of the research consisted of films from five Polish-speaking historical channels on YouTube, selected from among the most popular channels which did not belong to state institutions. The choice of those channels was based on their leading position in terms of reach on the Polish-speaking historical YouTube at the time (understood as the total and

² Wiktor Werner, Adrian Trzoss, Dawid Gralik, “History and YouTube. Historical narrative in the age of Web 2.0”, *Nauka* 3 (2020), 119–140.

³ Anna Barańska-Szmitko, “Dyskurs historyczny a dyskurs popularnonaukowy w serwisie YouTube na przykładzie wybranych kanałów”, *KULTURA – MEDIA – TEOLOGIA* 46 (2021): 160–187; Wiktor Werner, Adrian Trzoss, Dawid Gralik, “Media społecznościowe a funkcjonowanie wiedzy historycznej w Polsce. Raport z badań”, *Przegląd Archiwalno-Historyczny* VI (2019): 211–232; Anna Barańska-Szmitko, “Wyznaczniki tabloidyżacji popularnonaukowego dyskursu historycznego w kanale serwisu YouTube «Historia bez Cenzury»”, *Stylistyka* 31 (2022): 137–175.

⁴ Terms “annotated” and “tagged” are used interchangeably in the meaning of assigning a value (tag) within a given qualitative category.

mean numbers of views, comments, and subscribers⁵). Moreover, those channels displayed a broad range of subjects, contrary to hermetically sealed channels (such as *IrytującyHistoryk*, focused on the history of arms and armour). The study includes data from the period between December 2013 to April 2021, where the start date marks the launch of the oldest channels, which we assumed as the date of the chronologically earliest film published on one of the studied channels. The end date, 1 April 2021, is the date when the data were archived (scraped). A total of 551 films published on the following channels were included in the study: the oldest and largest of them, *Historia bez cenzury*⁶ (220 films), *Thrashing Mad*⁷ (139 films), *Historia w 5 minut*⁸ (69 films), *Oblicza XX wieku*⁹ (66 films) and *ciekawehistorie*¹⁰ (63 films), that is all productions on historical subjects published by these channels. The films were annotated using two sets of categories (tags).

The first set, related to the specificity of films as historical narratives, included the following elements:

- 1) indication of subject matter: political, military, social, cultural, economic,
- 2) indication of subject location: history of Poland and world history,
- 3) indication of period: Antiquity, Middle Ages, Modern Era, 19th C., 20th C., contemporary post-1989 and general, comprehensive films,
- 4) indication which type of phenomenon was the main object of the film and the object of history on which attention was focused: person, event, process or thing.

The other set of categories specifically addressed the presence of women in film:

- 1) Category one, gender, indicated films in which women were featured in any way or not at all (for films devoted solely to men), as well as those where the approach to the subject did not allow to differentiate genders at all (e.g., where states were discussed as wholes),
- 2) Category two addressed the specifics of women's presence: only implicitly suggested or indicated explicitly "by name",
- 3) Category three measured the degree of presence of the topic of women on a scale from 1 to 4. Values on this four-grade scale have the following meaning:

5 Werner, Trzoss, Gralik, „History and YouTube”.

6 *Historia bez cenzury*, YouTube, <https://www.youtube.com/user/HistoriaBezCenzuryMB> (accessed: 1.07.2021).

7 *Thrashing Mad*, YouTube, <https://www.youtube.com/user/ThrashingMadPL> (accessed: 1.07.2021).

8 *Historia w 5 minut*, YouTube, <https://www.youtube.com/c/Historiaw5minut> (accessed: 1.07.2021).

9 *Oblicza XX wieku*, YouTube, <https://www.youtube.com/c/ObliczaXXWiek> (accessed: 1.07.2021).

10 *ciekawehistorie*, YouTube, <https://www.youtube.com/c/ciekawehistorietv> (accessed: 1.07.2021).

1 – a brief mention of the female figure (e.g., as a factual information: “In 1386, Jagiełło married Jadwiga”), 2 – multiple mentions of various female figures and underlining their role in the main theme, 3 – emphasising female figures in the form of a separate, well-developed problem thread (e.g., the role of Margaret Thatcher in the fall of Communism), 4 – woman as the main figure of the film.

Also, data such as the number of views and the date of publication were collected for each film using the YouTube application programming interface (API) and an original computer programme written in Python for this purpose. The collected data were stored as a database.

2.2

The quantitative research was conducted in two stages. First, in order to study the interrelations between the specificity of historical narrative and the presence of women in film, we conducted a two-dimensional correspondence analysis of category pairs.

Correspondence analysis (CA) is a method which allows to determine relationships between categorised traits of studied objects. It is based on a contingency table containing the frequencies of objects sharing a certain pair of traits (where rows and columns represent each of the categories). Conceptually speaking, correspondence analysis is similar to principal component analysis (PCA). The difference between the two is that, instead of covariance matrix (which determines the deviation of continuous variables from linear correlation), inertia matrix is decomposed. Inertia is defined as the value of χ^2 (*Chi-square*) calculated on the basis of a contingency table for individual pairs of traits, normalized by the total number of objects (the terminology is derived from the analogy to the moment of inertia known in classical physics). Therefore, low inertia means a lack of or very small relationship between traits in a given row and column of the contingency table, whereas a high value of inertia indicated a strong relationship between traits.

The result of correspondence analysis is a collection of components and singular values (similar to the components and eigenvalues of PCA). The ratio of each singular value to the sum total of all singular values determines how much of variability can be described by the coordinate designated by corresponding components. Choosing components corresponding to two highest singular values as the basis makes it possible to present individual traits as points on a two-dimensional plane, where the distance between points in

the plane is inversely proportional to the frequency of co-occurrence of traits. The higher the inertia corresponding to a given coordinate, the more significant are distances along that coordinate.

Correspondence analysis¹¹ enables the reduction of dimensionality of problems and can be used irrespective of the statistical significance of the χ^2 test. The limitation of correspondence analysis is that the distance between points in row and column categories is not mathematically defined. Therefore, the interpretation of results requires caution and paying special attention to the degree of aggregation or proximity of points, depending on their position in the coordinate system. The example below is one of two-way cross tables used in the study, showing the frequency of co-occurrence of subject matter categories compared with the context of presence of women in films.

	economic	cultural	military	political	social
explicite	8	27	25	42	40
implicite	2	5	12	10	13
none	3	4	20	2	6

Figure 1: two-way cross table, topic and context of presence of women in films

The correspondence analysis for the above two-way cross tab was presented in a two-dimensional coordinate system with unequal inertia coefficients for each axis (99.71% and 0.29% for the X and Y axes, respectively).

¹¹ Dylan Glynn, *Correspondence analysis. Methods for Semantics: Quantitative Studies in Polysemy and Synonymy* (Amsterdam: John Benjamins Publishing Company, 2014), 443-485; Michael J. Greenacre, "Correspondence analysis", *Wiley Interdisciplinary Reviews: Computational Statistics* 2, 5 (2010), 613–619.

Figure 2: Correspondence relationship: topic–context (for all channels)

The second stage involved the analysis of data distribution for two fundamental parameters of the population of films: the number of views in a given category, designated as W , and the number of films in it, or N . The aim of such analysis was not only to find the significance (of size) of each category, but also to compare the numbers of views (W) and of films (N), which we defined as variable $k = \frac{W}{N}$. The values of the k ratio, which is our original development, are rounded up to two decimal places. The k value can be interpreted in three ways:

1. $k > 1$ means that the given category generates proportionally more views per film within the studied population,
2. $k = 1$ means that the given category generates the same number of views per film as other categories in the studied population,
3. $k < 1$ means that the given category generates proportionally fewer views per film within the studied population.

In the study we performed, only options 1 and 3 were present. Therefore, the question we ask in the context of each category is whether it is more popular than other categories according to the proportion designated as k . These data were visualised in pie charts distinguished by categories and their N and W parameters. Detailed values of k , related to the main research problem, that is, the comparison of k values for films in which men or women predominate, can be found below in the text. This comparison provides an answer to the fundamental question, whether the reception of films featuring men as main characters is proportionally higher than of those where the main characters are women (that is, if the condition $k > 1$ occurs for men, and the condition $k < 1$ for women, where the value in the category of scale is 3 or 4).

2.3

The research with qualitative methods involved identifying the specifics of selected films (with the most clearly portrayed female figures) in the context of rhetoric, prevailing metaphors, schemas, and story motifs.¹² The method of interpretation is rooted in Northrop Frye's concept of criticism of story motifs and archetypes proposed in his fundamental work *Anatomy of Criticism* (written in 1957; the 2000 edition was used).¹³ The typology of story schemes: comedy, epos, tragedy, irony and satire, along with their accompanying themes and prevalent metaphors, is of crucial importance to the interpretation of studied films. The intended use of Frye's concept, developed in the context of essential texts of culture and literature, was to analyse various narratives.¹⁴ Frye's typology was adapted for use in historiographical analysis, with success, by Hayden White in his monumental *Metahistory*¹⁵

¹² Wiktor Werner, "Poznawcza rola metafory w polskim dyskursie historyczno-politycznym po 1989 roku", in *Pamięć i polityka historyczna. Doświadczenia Polski i jej sąsiadów*, red. Sławomir M. Nowinowski, Jan Pomorski, Rafał Stobiecki (Łódź: Instytut Pamięci Narodowej, 2008), 91–105.

¹³Northrop Frye, *Anatomy of Criticism. Four Essays* (Princeton: Princeton University Press, 2000).

¹⁴ N. Frye, *Anatomy*, 48-49, 104.

¹⁵ Hayden White, *Metahistory. Historical Imagination in Nineteenth-Century Europe* (Baltimore-London: JHU Press, 1975).

and other researchers using the methods of criticism of themes, narrative forms, and historiographical metaphors.¹⁶

A combination of research method was adopted: quantitative methods (correspondence analysis and descriptive statistics) were used in parallel to qualitative methods (criticism of story motifs and dominant metaphors). The task of the correspondence analysis method is to describe the relationship between categories using quantitative parameters to objectivise the research process. This aim was defined for this method in the French school of sociology by Jean Paul Benzécri, who introduced computational methods on a large scale to the study of social and linguistic phenomena.¹⁷ We believe that, by using a combination of culturally objectivising and localising methods, it will be possible to remove the limitations of each of those methods used separately. We mitigated the risk of formulating inadequate claims due to the reduction of the cultural sense of studied phenomena and the risk of projecting our own values onto the studied world associated with limiting oneself to hermeneutical methods only.

3. Results of the study for individual channels

3.1

The channel *Historia bez cenzury* (History uncensored), founded in 2013, is currently¹⁸ the most popular channel devoted to history on Polish-speaking YouTube. Established at the initiative of its producer, Tomasz Okoń, the channel now has an executive team of four people: host of the programme Wojciech Drewniak (master's degree in history), editor Kamil Pankanin, researcher Paweł Chilczuk (master's degree in history, historical consultant), responsible for querying the matters under discussion, and the producer himself. The channel aims to be entertaining, emphasising the stage presence of its charismatic host and the visual layer accompanying its humorous presentations. Women's themes are present (in any form) in 185 of 220 films on this channel, with women being shown explicitly as specific individuals in 143 of those 185 films. There were 18 films on this channel where a woman was the main character (April 2021). The analysis of the materials showed a correspondence between the presence of women in films and social, political, and cultural themes, whereas

16 Wojciech Wrzosek, *Historia-kultura-metafora: powstanie nieklasycznej historiografii* (Wrocław: Fundacja na rzecz Nauki Polskiej, 1995); Wiktor Werner, John William Draper, Andrew Dickson, "White wobec wojny nauki z religią. Rola metafory historiograficznej", *Kwartalnik Historii Nauki i Techniki* 49, 1 (2004): 1, 7–27.

17 Jean Paul Benzécri, "El análisis de correspondencias", *Cahiers de l'analyse des données* 2, nr 2 (1977): 125–142; Benzécri, "Typologie de textes grecs d'après les occurrences des formes des mots outils", *Cahiers de l'analyse des données* 16, 1 (1991): 61–86.

18 On the date when research material was archived.

“purely” men’s films were closer to economic and military themes. Women’s themes also turned out closer to the process-focused perspective, while purely men’s ones were strongly adjacent to the event-focused perspective, as shown in the following quantitative correspondence table (number of films tagged with each category):

Figure 3: Correspondence relationship: Topic – gender (for Historia bez cenzury)

historical object	person	process	thing	event
women	85	57	15	27
men	9	6	5	14

3.2

The channel *Historia w 5 minut* (History in 5 minutes) exists since 2016, when it debuted with the film “Bitwa pod Połonką 1660” (Battle of Połonka, 1660). That film launched one of the channel’s many series, focused on the history of Poland. The author of

Historia w 5 minut is Dawid Rodenko. Its name refers to the length of the early films on the channel. The content uploaded to the channel now is longer, with some films reaching 40 minutes. Most films on the channel relate to economic and political history. The channel's topics mainly focus on the nineteenth and twentieth century period (even though its Author, as he declared himself, is most interested in ancient Rome). The presented content is richly illustrated with graphics and maps. Women's themes, in any form, appear in 41 of 69 films, whereas women are the main figures (rated 4 on our scale) in only two films. Correspondence analysis indicates a relationship between the presence of women in a film and the process-focused perspective, whereas men's themes prevail wherever the film focuses on specific figures or events, or on military topics, from which, however, female figures are not excluded. Relationships for the number of films in terms of the presence of women and the construction of narrative from the viewpoint of the narrative-making phenomenon, or historical objects (people, processes, things or events) and the dominant subject matter, are shown below:

historical object	personal	process	thing	event
feminine	7	24	1	8
masculine	8	9	1	10

Subject matter	cultural	military	political	social
feminine	3	7	20	10
masculine	3	9	13	3

3.3

Oblicza XX wieku (Faces of the 20th century) is a channel founded by Bartosz Borkowski, a historian and journalist. Its first film premiered on 11 November 2017. In terms of chronology, the channel stays limited, true to its name, to the history of twentieth century. Initially, the plan was to focus only on the topic of the inter-war period, yet with time it was decided to broaden the scope to cover the whole century. Still, the vast majority of films involves the 1918–1945 period. Women's themes in any form can be found in 56 of 66 films, yet in no film a woman is the main figure. They also correspond positively with political

questions and a focus on historical processes. In the case of purely men’s themes, no clear correspondences were found. The tables below show the relationships between categories:

object	personal	process	event
women	18	14	23
men	1	2	7

subject matter	Economic	cultural	military	political	social
feminine	5	3	9	28	11
masculine	0	0	2	5	3

3.4

The channel *ciekawehistorie* (Interesting histories) was launched on 9 January 2018 by Tomasz Czukiewski – a self-confessed journalist by vocation and education.¹⁹ The films on this channel are composed of video, audio, and photographic material selected by the author, with added commentary to introduce or explain each event to the viewer but without any guiding narrative, which allows the materials to “speak for themselves”. The topics are focused mainly on the history of 20th century and contemporary history (seldom later than the 1930s). In films on more recent topics, there are interviews with participants of the presented events. Out of 69 films, women are present in 53, and a woman is the main figure (rated 4 on the scale) in 6. The prevalent object matter of films featuring women is political and military, whereas the films devoted only to men correspond with social and economic themes. The presence of women in films also corresponds with the processual and personal approach. The tables below show quantitative relationships:

object	personal	process	thing	event
women	20	16	2	14
men	2	1	0	6

¹⁹ Tomasz Czukiewski, “Moje wpisy”, naTemat, <https://natemat.pl/blogi/tomaszczukiewski> (accessed: 1.05.2022).

Subject matter	cultural	military	political	social
feminine	3	6	31	12
masculine	0	1	4	4

3.5

ThrashingMadPL is a channel operated by Arkadiusz Michalski, which has been present on YouTube since February 2013.²⁰ During that time, it managed to gather more than 100 thousand subscribers, produce over 600 films, and break the barrier of 30 million views of the channel. Initially the channel focused on video games, then educational materials related to the beginnings of the Polish state started to appear there. Currently the *ThrashingMadPL* channel focuses solely on producing educational contents, collected in the series “Historia na Szybko” (Quick history). The series is based on original graphics prepared by the author coupled with a factual description of the events discussed, presented as an audio narrative. The author also notes that each episode is prepared after meticulous research. However, the sources he uses are not usually revealed to the viewers. The series can be divided into three sub-series: “History of Poland”, “State Borders”, and aggregated materials related to world history questions. In the case of the “History of Poland” and world history questions, the narration is conducted in a form characteristic of school education, that is, the narrative is driven by the figures of subsequent rulers and momentous events. Women are present in 101 of 139 films, but only one film has a woman as the main figure. Women most often appear in politically themed films, while men accompany military history, which seems to follow the premise that the narrative is carried out in a school-like manner. Furthermore, men featured as protagonists of productions are more often presented from a personal/biographical perspective.

²⁰ History was not the original subject matter of the channel. Its author launched it with a gameplay series, then later switched to historical subjects. All noise related to this change were eliminated in the study at the stage of preprocessing of archived data.

Figure 4: Correspondence relationship: object – gender (for the channel ThrashingMadPL)

Figure 5: Correspondence relationship: theme – gender (for the channel ThrashingMadPL)

4. Summary results of the study

A total of 551 films were included in research, of which 430 were qualified as including female figures, 112 as devoted to men only, and 8 as films where the topic of gender could not be clearly determined (as the films referred to entire “states” or “nations”). For films featuring women, the median of views was 493.28 thousand views per film, whereas for “purely masculine” films it equalled 145.5 thousand views.

The correspondence analysis conducted for the summary table containing the data of all channels indicated the proximity between films featuring women and the political,

cultural, and economic thematic categories, whereas the exclusively “masculine” films clearly corresponded with military topics.

Figure 6: Correspondence relationship: theme – gender (for all channels)

The quantitative data for all channels can also be presented as the relationship between the number of films in specific categories and the number of views of those films, as shown in the pie charts below.

Figure 7: The percentage share of films and views in individual research categories. The inner and outer doughnuts show, respectively, the percentage of the number of views and the number of films in each given category.

Figure 8: The percentage share of individual categories in all films.

The presented pie charts show that films displaying the full picture of history (with both female and male figures) predominate in the global overview, while the films focusing exclusively on masculine topics are a minority in terms of both the number of films and of viewership. On the other hand, films where women are main protagonists are not a majority either.

5. Qualitative interpretation

The qualitative interpretation, which we based on Northrop Frye's typology of fictional schemes and motifs, involved 26 films selected from the whole collection subjected to quantitative analysis. Only the films in which women were main characters, that is, which were rated 4 on the scale we developed, were selected. It was important for us to focus on narratives wholly devoted to women, and not on anecdotal factual mentions (rated 1, e.g., "in 965 Mieszko married Doubravka") or short and shallow threads (rated 2), devoid of any significant narrative significance (metaphors, symbols, evaluations) for the entire film.

Even though the analysed productions have the characteristics of the distinct style of each channel, they differ in the specific ways of describing women and the events associated with them. In the *Historia bez cenzury* channel, there is a clear division of "feminine" films into those sharing fictional schemes of comedy, satire, and the epic scheme. The scheme of comedy, defined by Frye as the scheme or mythos of spring²¹, is characterised by a narrative levity. It is joyful and ribald, frequently willing to engage in erotic themes. It emphasises the tensions between the liveliness and youth, and decrepitude and old age; between cunning and gullibility, and between luck (prosperity) and misfortune. As a rule, comedy avoids moral valuation. Instead, victories and defeats tend to result from the natural order of things (old age has to give way to youth, gullibility must lose to cunning, a lucky man prevail over a luckless one, a strong man beat a weakling). The film "Napalona Caryca - Katarzyna Wielka"²² (Horny Empress - Catherine the Great) is definitely comedic in character. While the authors joke about her sexual temperament, they do not pass a moral judgment of it but appreciate her political and economic achievements. The Empress is presented as a comedic character: a personification of certain traits (vigour, cunning, strength) rather than an individual to be judged morally. The jokes are neither bitter or malicious, and the admiration of the achievements is genuine. The films by *Historia bez cenzury* about sexual mores, "Starożytna prostytutka"²³ (Ancient prostitution) and "Seks w średniowieczu" (Sex in the Middle Ages) are generally comedic in character (the latter shows some traits of satire at times, which we shall discuss later). Sexuality is treated here more as a sign of normality than

21 Frye, *Anatomy*, 163–180.

22 "Napalona caryca – Katarzyna Wielka", *Historia bez cenzury*, 11.07.2019, YouTube, 15:44, <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=rks4lr7NFZw> (accessed: 1.03.2022).

23 "Starożytna prostytutka", *Historia bez cenzury*, 5.10.2015, YouTube, 11:47, <https://youtu.be/LbaY5GJPjA> (accessed: 1.02.2022).

an aberration, and the hostile attitude of medieval clergy towards erotic life is shown as an attempt to create a topsy-turvy world.²⁴

Women featured on the *Historia bez cenzury* channel are quite often describes as epic characters. The epic scheme²⁵ (“romance” in Frye’ work, which sometimes leads Polish authors to translate it as “romantic”, causing misunderstandings) is predominant in the film devoted to Emilia Plater²⁶ and is also present in the film about Marie Skłodowska–Curie.²⁷ The essential motifs found in the epic scheme, characterised with greater maturity and thus called the “summer” scheme by Frye, are the motif of struggle (*agon*) against the adversities of fate, the narrative mood of threat and combat (*pathos*), and the process of maturation and gaining social recognition in the fire of battle and adversity (*anagnorisis*). The term *anagnorisis* literally means “recognition”, as the heroine recognises her strength, her value, and also gains the recognition of her milieu. The film of a clearly epic character is “Polska Królowa Wikingów”²⁸ (Polish Queen of the Vikings) by *Historia bez Cenzury*, where the importance of *agon* and *anagnorisis* is crucial. The narrator of the film emphasises the heroic deeds of the protagonists and the regard she enjoyed.

Moral valuation is present in the epic scheme, as the deeds of the heroines prove their worth. There is also an indication of good and evil, between which the heroines choose: this aspect is particularly poignant in the films about Emilia Plater and Świątosława.

In narrative practice, the epic scheme may show features of both comedy and tragedy. The epic scheme with comedic traits can be found in films dedicated to Queen Jadwiga (both the one shown on the channel *Historia bez cenzury*²⁹ and the one on *ThrashingMadPL*³⁰). In both cases, the frame of the narration includes sudden plot twists (*peripeteias*), expose tumultuous events, albeit presented as comical, such as the failed “consummation” of marriage between Jadwiga and William of Habsburg, since she was prevented from axing down the door (through which she wanted to escape to her fiancé) by Polish lords, who then expelled the miserable groom from Kraków. In this context historical figures are being shown

24 “Seks w średniowieczu”, *Historia bez cenzury*, 22.09.2016, YouTube, 14:30, <https://youtu.be/2bwp2lOK4xc> (accessed: 1.02.2022).

25 Frye, *Anatomy*, 186–200.

26 “Dziewica bohater – Emilia Plater”, *Historia bez cenzury*, 26.01.2016, YouTube, 16:11, <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=8nE65OpyqvY> (dostęp: 1.02.2022).

27 „Dziewczę z charakterem – Maria Skłodowska-Curie”, *Historia bez cenzury*, 6.03.2014, YouTube, 11:47, <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Uw2YU9TdnOA> (dostęp: 1.02.2022).

28 “Polska Królowa Wikingów”, *Historia bez cenzury*, 5.07.2015, YouTube, 10:15, <https://youtu.be/2oUDCX13zC0> (dostęp: 1.02.2022).

29 “Baba z berłem – Jadwiga”, *Historia bez cenzury*, 29.12.2016, YouTube, 15:38, <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=kpWZoUX55q0> (accessed: 1.02.2022).

30 “Jadwiga (Historia Polski #79) (Lata 1384-1386)”, *ThrashingMadPL*, 5.09.2019, YouTube, 17:03, <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=OHGe5whQIuY&t> (accessed: 1.02.2022).

in a typically comedic style. Both Habsburg and Siemowit IV appear as “false heroes”: one as a “sham” would-be husband, the other as a false, “unlucky” suitor–kidnapper. Simultaneously, the background of the narrative shows a serious political struggle for power that would decide the future of several thrones, adding epic elements to a comedic plot. Another film of such an epic character (with a strong comedic element) is devoted to Krystyna Skarbak.³¹ Within, her heroic actions and recognition as an exceptionally gifted special forces operative are mixed with the emphasis on her sexual temperament and numerous erotic adventures.

The combination of epic and tragedy underscores the suffering of the heroes and the sacrifice they made in their struggle with adversities and to achieve positive goals (freedom of the country, human life). The video by *Historia bez cenzury* about Irena Sendler³² is an epic film containing elements of tragic rhetoric (related to the traits of the world where the events take place). A combination of the epic and tragic schemes is also present in the film “Auschwitz. Niesamowita ucieczka zakochanej pary”³³ (Auschwitz: The amazing escape of a couple in love) on the channel *ciekawehistorie*. It shows the struggle against adverse fate (destiny), characteristic of the tragedy scheme³⁴, albeit with the epic remark that the adversities can be overcome, and that love can prevail over hostile fate.

The pure scheme of tragedy, where the emphasis is on the suffering and sacrifice, quite often correlates with historical narrative, and can very frequently be found in the film presented on YouTube. Such is the character of some films showing the history of Poland produced by state institutions (e.g., IPN).³⁵ Even though commercial channels do not refer to this style that often when covering the same subject (the history of Poland), one can find some films created in that style. One such example is the film on the channel *Historia w 5 minut* entitled “II Rzeczpospolita. Historia w Pigułce”³⁶ (Second Republic: History in a nutshell). The film is black-and-white and made with great care. Most noteworthy, it is a fully fledged film etude with decorations and actors wearing period garments. Its plot is the story of Tadeusz Dołęga-Mostowicz who, upon request by Melchior Wańkowicz, travels across

31 “Sex, wojna i dynamit – Krystyna Skarbak”, *Historia bez cenzury*, 14.03.2015, YouTube, 14:37, <https://youtu.be/Jk6icnCkySA> (accessed: 1.02.2022).

32 “Jak Polacy ratowali Żydów #1. Irena Sendlerowa”, *Historia bez cenzury*, 15.02.2018, YouTube, 16:42, <https://youtu.be/Axs2OP3nOIY> (accessed: 1.02.2022).

33 “Auschwitz. Niesamowita ucieczka zakochanej pary”, *ciekawehistorie*, 7.02.2018, YouTube, 13:17, <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=67xIucpbldo> (accessed: 1.02.2022).

34 Frye, *Anatomy*, 206–220.

35 Wiktor Werner, Dawid Gralik, Adrian Trzoss, “Polish Historical Narration and National Identity in the Light of Studies at Youtube”, *Historyka Studia Metodologiczne* 51, Spec. Iss. (2021): 223–249.

36 II Rzeczpospolita. Historia w Pigułce”, *Historia w 5 minut*, 10.11.2019, YouTube, 22:49, <https://youtu.be/waFQIT2xcWQ> (dostęp: 1.02.2022).

Poland accompanied by a female assistant (a fully developed film character) interviewing people important for the Second Polish Republic. Despite the apparently idyllic character of the story, the viewers are always aware of the tragic fate, the dark destiny awaiting the figures presented in the film. We meet Father Maximilian Kolbe, Janusz Kusociński, and Witold Zacharewicz, all murdered by Germans, as well as other people, whose lives are bound to end in tragedy. Such is also the case of the narrator himself, Tadeusz Dołęga-Mostowicz, who died on 20 September 1939. The world presented in the film is a doomed world, which we, the viewers, know very well. The happiness of its characters, their life optimism, and serenity only amplify the tragic meaning of the narrative.

The analysed films also contain mature, “winter” schemas of irony and satire.³⁷ Satire focuses on showing an upside-down world³⁸, that is a reality dominated by absurd, scandalous, and even criminal phenomena and events. Such a world can either be real enough (while remaining an aberration in terms of its existing “moral order”) or be a mock reality, which awaits demystification.

The film by *Historia bez cenzury* entitled “Krwawa hrabina? Elżbieta Batory”³⁹ (Bloody Countess? Elizabeth Báthory) is clearly satirical in character. Initially, the narrator tells a frightening story about the crimes and deviancy of Elizabeth Báthory, with the emphasis characteristic of himself and the mood of the channel, only to admit at one point that these revelations were all false (though from the period), created to divest the protagonist of her wealth in favour of the Habsburgs ruling in Hungary. The film “Czarująca s.ka – Agnieszka Machówna” (Charming b.tch – Agnieszka Machówna), also by *Historia bez cenzury*, is also a satire (with comedic elements), where the upside-down world results from the violation of laws and mores by the protagonist, a seventeenth-century marriage fraudster of peasant origin, who could not only seduce magnates of the epoch but even lead them to the altar. The title character is a “false bride”, a false hero figure typical of satire and comedy. The influence of the satire scheme is also visible in the film about Tamara Łempicka (*Historia bez cenzury*).⁴⁰ The specific upside-down world is punctuated by the strong emphasis not on the protagonist’s artwork (indeed, her paintings are shown in the visual layer of the film) but on her unbridled sexual life. An “upside-down world” can also mean the Byzantine empire

37 Frye, *Anatomy*, 223–239.

38 Frye, *Anatomy*, 225–226.

39 “Krwawa hrabina? Elżbieta Batory”, *Historia bez cenzury*, 27.06.2017, YouTube, 16:09, <https://youtu.be/u3ddO73cYt0> (accessed: 1.02.2022).

40 “Orgie, koks i sztuka – Tamara Łempicka”, *Historia bez cenzury*, 10.06.2021, YouTube, 17:56, <https://youtu.be/pFUUiWu9lfM> (accessed: 1.02.2022).

where a prostitute sits on the throne.⁴¹ Satire is a very flexible scheme, able to absorb a variety of contents. Its similarity to comedy is conspicuous due to the similarity of characters: first of all, due to the presence of “false heroes”, whose actual natures clash with the public functions they perform. Such juxtapositions as matron–whore or knight–coward are characteristic of satire but also familiar to comedy. The difference, however, lies in the atmosphere of the story and the way how the world is described. Being the juvenile style, comedy depicts the world in its most vital aspect: its propensity not to mind its words when highlighting the flaws and weaknesses of characters is the child’s ability to tell the truth that the king is naked. The reality of comedy is a world in which laws are in place, and the characters are subjected to those laws, whereas in the universe of satire, laws give way to anomalies. We see it from the perspective of an old man who discerns the errors and deviations stacked upon one another. It results in different attitudes towards sexuality. The juvenile narrator of comedy sees sex as the energy and embodiment of laws existing in the world: the laws of fertility, vitality, and joy of life. As the mature, even senile author of satire seeks perversion, deviation, indulgence, and abuse. his perception is tainted with acerbity and much more distanced than that of affirmative comedy. Sexuality, however, is not tied to the schema of satire, which may not adduce this aspect of human life at all, like in the film “Trzy osoby w jednym ciele - historia Chris Sizemore” (Three people in one body: The history of Chris Sizemore), published on the channel *ciekawehistorie*⁴², where the upside-down world is related to the title character’s dissociated personality, or like in the film by *Historia w 5 minut* entitled “Wywiad po narkotykach, 1953 rok”⁴³ (Interview on drugs, 1953), where the false reality refers to the world experienced by the protagonist answering questions under the influence of drugs.

An interesting process, already begun in satire, develops in the schema of irony, a process that creates distance between the narrator and the described events. A distance that might mean that the story suggests that the true meaning of the narrated events is entirely different from that which flows directly from the story.

The film on the *ciekawehistorie* channel, “Stalinowska propaganda na przykładzie filmu «Upadek Berlina»”⁴⁴ (Stalinist propaganda on the example of the film «The fall of

41 “Dziwka na tronie – Teodora”, *Historia bez cenzury*, 1.03.2018, YouTube, 13:46, https://youtu.be/tYmF5aEk_Mw (accessed: 1.02.2022).

42 “Trzy osoby w jednym ciele – historia Chris Sizemore”, *ciekawehistorie*, 3.02.2019, YouTube, 9:38, <https://youtu.be/D3prSAi-pm8> (dostęp: 1.02.2022).

43 “Wywiad po narkotykach, 1953 rok”, *Historia w 5 minut*, 16.01.2019, YouTube, 3:21, https://youtu.be/Sm77bt_9QpU (dostęp: 1.02.2022).

44 “Stalinowska propaganda na przykładzie filmu «Upadek Berlina»”, *ciekawehistorie*, 12.07.2018, YouTube, [no duration], <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=-1lwDb6VqV8> (accessed: 1.02.2022).

Berlin»), has such an ironic, distanced character. Watching this film we see an epic and romantic tale of love and the triumph of good against evil, yet we remain aware that the (historical) reality was entirely different. As the narrator distances himself from the narrative, the character as the main person on whom the narrative is focused fades away. The centre of attention shifts to the mechanisms of reality: pointing them out turns out to be the actual aim of the narrative, the character figure merely a pretext. This component of the irony/satire scheme is clear in the film “Reklamy, które dziś byłyby zakazane”⁴⁵ (Advertising that would be forbidden today), which shows the stereotype of a woman focused on the kitchen, children, and pampering her husband as the product of a certain social practice expressed through ads. The scheme of irony (with elements of satire) is also present in the film “Putin vs Megyn Kelly (amerykańska dziennikarka)”⁴⁶ (Putin vs Megyn Kelly, American journalist). There are two levels of irony there: Putin himself is ironic, using his informational advantage (not to mention the advantage from training at the Leningrad school of Committee for State Security, hereafter as KGB) over the journalist to deride her questions. He makes fun of her lack of access to secret information he obviously does have. Finally, there is a deeper level of irony, not available to all viewers, involving the fact that at least some of them may assume that Putin is most likely lying, and that, actually, the operational activities he denies may have taken place. Even so, we are under the impression that he is right, and the journalist is wrong. A similar irony can frequently be found in literature, where a naive or even silly character tells the truth, whereas a brilliant and intelligent protagonist lies. The classic example of it is the confrontation between elegant Don Juan and his rude servant Sganarel in Molière’s play. The irony in the Putin–Kelly interview is that the not too feisty and highly nervous woman is most likely the bearer of truth, whereas the man – backed by enormous self-confidence and the power of intelligence services of a great power – lies.

6. Conclusions

To interpret the results, we cannot avoid the context of the medium as the place where the narratives we analyse are created and function. On the one hand, history on YouTube takes on a ludic aspect.⁴⁷ On the other (especially in the case of channels other than *Historia bez*

45 “Reklamy, które dziś byłyby zakazane”, ciekawehistorie, 5.07.2019, YouTube, 8:10, <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=ksrrW0GHSfE> (accessed: 1.02.2022).

46 “Putin vs Megyn Kelly (amerykańska dziennikarka)”, ciekawehistorie, [no publication date], YouTube, [no duration], <https://youtu.be/s9fQEPVUZCQ> (accessed: 1.02.2022).

47 Adrian Trzoss, “Cyfrowy Homo Ludens. Historia jako element obszaru rozrywki na portalu społecznościowym Youtube, Popularyzacja nauk historycznych – teoria i praktyka”, in *Popularyzacja nauk historycznych – teoria i praktyka. Zbiór studiów*, red. Dominika Gołaszewska-Rusinowska, Małgorzata Mielewska, Tomasz Sińczak (Toruń: Instytut Promocji Historii, 2018): 194–209.

cenzury) the edutainment component is clearly visible.⁴⁸ The latter in particular can be seen as the narrative bridge between school education and social media. It may yet become a successful counter to the strong and effective tendency to tabloidise historical narratives. The “historically captive minds” discussed by Jan Pomorski⁴⁹ are the next piece of the puzzle. They should be treated as pre-formatted expectations, or perhaps habits, of potential recipients with regard to certain narrative forms (with an emphasis on the aforesaid tabloidisation and ludic quality). The digital *homo ludens* seems to resonate with the viewers’ expectations that a historical narrative should be a tale of people and their humanity: sexuality, adventures, heroic struggles. About real people, of flesh and blood, more like us than their bronze statues or factual material at school. Furthermore, the sexualised image, primarily of women, is compatible with the nature of YouTube as a visual medium. Thus, the emphasis on visual aspects seems to be yet another element to attract viewership, at the same time hanging on the stereotype and carnality of women to a greater extent than on men and their “historical achievements”. It presents a certain continuum⁵⁰, which only strengthens the premise that viewers’ expectations are pre-formatted, and the tabloidisation tactic is successful.

The largest and most influential historical channel on the Polish-speaking YouTube, from the viewpoint of films presented there, is *Historia bez cenzury*.⁵¹ The films on that channel usually show women using the style of comedy and satire. It should be noted that that style is clearly predominant there. The schema of satire enables showing events that are both scandalous and fascinating, which is characteristic of the tabloid-like media. Admittedly, some of the films devoted to women are epic in character, but it is a minority (the epic style is used to describe men more often). The heroines of films on *Historia bez cenzury* are also sexualised more often than male heroes. Out of all female protagonists, only Emilia Plater and Elizabeth of Poland avoided this fate. In the case of Marie Curie, the sexual motifs are clearly outlined, though the film maintains the epic style. Such a tendency to expose the sexual aspect of human nature more strongly in describing women compared to men is much

48 Anna Barańska-Szmitko, „Dyskurs historyczny a dyskurs popularnonaukowy w serwisie YouTube na przykładzie wybranych kanałów”, *Kultura-Media-Teologia* 46 (2021), 160–187.

49 Jan Pomorski, “Edukacja historyczna u progu XXI wieku”, in *Po co uczyć historii?*, red. Czesław Majorek (Warszawa: COMSNP, 1988), 239–253.

50 Giovanni Sartori, *Homo videns: televisione e post-pensiero* (Gius. Laterza & Figli Spa, 2014).

51 Other, though clearly smaller than the ones described here, are the following channels we did not analyse: *Powojnie*; *Tu Historia - Joanna Jasitczak*; *Okupowana Polska*; *Irytujący historyk*; *Światowa historia*; *Na bitewnym szlaku*; *Historia wojny nieznanej* (inactive); *AleHistoria* (inactive); *Historyczny Top*; *Karolina Żebrowska*; *Grzegorz Bobrek*.

more visible in *Historia bez cenzury* than any other channel analysed here. It may be somewhat explained by referring to the clearly inflammatory nature of the medium. The other historical channel chose a different development path, the path of edutainment. The schemes of tragedy and irony, characterised by more gravity than the comedy and satire *Historia bez cenzury* prefers, also appear more frequently there. The larger history channel in Poland focuses on attracting mainly a teenage (and male) audience, which is consistent with the Web 2.0 feedback loop we referred to at the beginning of the article. However, if we look at historical channels as a whole, we shall observe (as the quantitative perspective shows) a significant presence of female figures, as well as their presence in the cross-section of the subject matter and chronology. The most general conclusion to be drawn here is that the creators of historical channels notice the ubiquity of women in history and do not overlook women's themes. The way of presenting the heroines of historical events, however, is affected by the specifics of the media, particularly the inflammatory, tabloid nature of the largest historical channel, *Historia bez cenzury*.

At a detailed level, however, it should be noted that the sexualisation itself is not one-dimensional. In the case of *Historia bez cenzury*, which resonates with Frye's typology, sexualisation is shown in its positive aspect when it serves the higher goal (patriotism) or reinforces the strong position of the hero, and in a clearly negative one when associated with perversion or submission.

The reason for this situation should also be explained. The nature of *Historia bez cenzury* seems to reflect the standards of the previous decade, where controversy and tabloidisation were the mainstream way of gaining popularity, whereas currently "education through entertainment" plays a more important role on YouTube, and the rising trend of that channel⁵² slows down. This change may possibly be explained as generational, since Generation Z entered the stage. It would require further research, however, for the reason that YouTube as a medium is constantly developing.

In conclusion, the thesis that historical narrative is dominated by men is not confirmed at the level of content of analysed sources, while the importance of women is accentuated more and more frequently. The changing proportions is clearly shown by the statistics of the materials we analysed (the k value). While in the case of purely "masculine" films, representing 20% of films, 15% of views were generated (the ratio of the number of views W to the number of films N , $k=0.75$), the ratio for purely "feminine" ones is significantly more

52 Wiktor Werner, Adrian Trzoss, Dawid Gralik, "History and YouTube. Historical narrative in the age of Web 2.0", *Nauka* 3 (2020), 119–140.

favourable: 5% of films generated 8% of views ($k=1.6$). Likewise, a higher ratio ($k=1.31$) is shown by films where distinct and significant appear, and the heroines are shown as agents (rated 3 on our scale). In terms of quantity, therefore, the total domination of “masculine subject matters” becomes history, the observable trend is rather to balance the female and male figures in historical narratives, with the reservation that there is still a certain mismatch in the discussed medium. In the context of the correspondence analysis we carried out, it can be said that the presence of women is indispensable in historical narratives pertaining to any political, economic and cultural issues (though it is possible to place female figures in the “back rank”). Virtually only military subjects make it possible not to mention women. Our research, both quantitative (correspondence analysis, statistical analysis) and qualitative (analysis of story schemes) indicate that YouTube, as a Web 2.0 medium, created new models of communication and operation of historical narratives, breaking the patterns of traditional literature and outright competing with the traditional forms of conveying historical knowledge such as textbooks and popular scientific books.

Acknowledgements

The research was funded by the NCN grant № 2020/39/B/HS3/01237 “Historical narratives in Web 2.0 as a functional element of national identities in Central and Eastern Europe”. The computations were performed on the computing cloud of the Centre of Informatics Tricity Academic Supercomputer and Network.